

A STUDY TO ASSESS THE PARENTAL ATTITUDE REGARDING JUNK FOOD CONSUMPTION AMONG CHILDREN VISITING SELECTED HOSPITAL, KOZHIKODE

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ABSTRACT

Junk foods are defined as high energy foods with minimal nutritional value, with higher content of saturated fat. Globally, Junk foods are popular among all age groups, but children are more to get attracted. Junk food consumption are associated with a high prevalence of obesity contributing to Hypertension, Type2 Diabetesmellitus, and cardiovascular diseases. Though its adverse health consequences are widely prevalent in all age groups, children and adolescents are more at risk. It may lead to obesity and act as a risk factor for different non-communicable diseases (NCD's) like heart diseases, cardiovascular disease, cancer, hypertension, diabetes, etc.^[1,2] **Objective:** assess the parental attitude regarding junk food consumption among children. **Methods:** A descriptive study design was adopted in order to assess parental attitude regarding junk food consumption among 65 children aged 5-10 years in selected hospital, Calicut. Non-probability purposive sampling method was used. Pilot study was conducted to find-out the feasibility of the study. The tools used were demographic proforma and attitude rating scale. Data collected from the subjects were analyzed by descriptive and inferential statistics. **Results:** In the samples 33.8% were belongs 20–30-year age group, 55.4% were between the group of 31-40 years, 10.8% were belongs to 41-50 years. 20% were male and 78.5 % were female. 56.9% belongs to Hindu religion, 33.8% were belongs to Muslim religion and 9.2% were Christians. 35.4 % belongs to daily wager, 55.4% are private employees, 7.7% are government employees, and 1.5 % are health workers. majority (47.7%) of the mothers are housewives, 30.8% are private employees, 9.25 are government employees, and 9.2% are health workers. majority (36.9%) receive annual income more than 20000 rupees, 21.5% receive between 15001-20000 rupees, 7.7% receive between 10001-15000 rupees 21.5% receive between 5001-10000 rupees and 10.8% receive less than 5000 rupees annually. majority (69.2%) belongs to nuclear family, 27.7% from joint family, and 1.5% from extended family. 44.61% belongs to primary, 41.54% belongs to lower primary, 12.31% belongs to upper primary classes. 44.6% belongs to government school, 47.7% belongs to private schools and 7.7 % belongs to others. majority of children (46.2%) are using private vehicles, 32.3% using school vehicles, 12.3% using public vehicles and 9.2% belongs to other modes of transportation. majority (67.7%) have satisfactory attitude towards junk food consumption, 26.2% shows non favourable attitude and 6.25 shows favourable attitude. **Conclusion:** The findings of the study showed that the majority of parents having a satisfactory attitude towards junk food consumption among their children. There is no significant association between the parental attitude with selected demographic variables.

KEYWORDS: parental attitude, junk food, children.

INTRODUCTION

In India, Globalization has caused nutritional transition from home cooked foods to processed sugary and spicy

snacks.^[3] The world population has reached above 8 billion according to the US Census Bureau International database. From this, more than 2 billion are the children who aged between 0-14 years. 1/3rd (36.3%) of these 2 billion children consumes fast food on a given day from the studies between 2015 -2018⁴. Indian population has reached around 141.7crores becoming the most populous country in the world. 25% of them are children and they are the backbone of the coming Indian future.^[4]

As per the reports, 59% of children between 14-17 years of age consumes packed foods and beverages at least once a day. Same with 51% and 35% in children between 11-13years and 9-10years respectively.^[5] Once the environment can influence the food styles, parents play a crucial role for physical and psychological development of the children. Parents influences them through attitudes, behaviours and feeding styles.^[6] Parents play a pivotal role in the development of their child's food preferences and energy intake, with research indicating that certain child feeding practices, such as exerting excessive control over what and how much children eat, may contribute to childhood overweight. Mothers are of particular interest on children's eating behaviour, as they have been shown to spend significantly more time than fathers in direct interactions with their children across several familial situations.

Section A: Analysis of socio demographic characteristics of parents of children between 5- 10 years.

Table 1: demographic characteristics of study participants. (n=65)

Sl No.	Variables	Frequency f	Percentage %
1	Age		
	20-30 years	22	33.8
	31-40 Years	36	55.4
	41-50 Years	07	10.8
2	Gender		
	Female	51	78.5
	Male	13	98.5
3	Religion		
	Hindu	37	56.9
	Islam	22	33.8
	Chrisian	6	9.2
4	Occupation of father		
	Daily wager	23	35.4
	Private employee	36	55.4
	Government employee	05	7.7
	Health worker	1	1.5
5	Occupation of mother		
	Housewife	31	47.7
	Private employee	20	30.8
	Government employee	06	9.25
	Health worker	6	9.2
6	Annual Income		
	<5000 Rupees	07	10.8
	5001-10000 Rupees	14	21.5
	10001-15000 Rupees	05	7.7
	15000-20000 Rupees	14	21.5
	>20000 Rupees	24	36.9
7	Family Structure		
	Nuclear Family	45	69.2
	Joint Family	18	27.7

MATERILAS AND METHODS

The study was done in Aster MIMS Hospital, Calicut, Kerala. The study has been taken up to assess the parental attitude regarding junk food consumption among children visiting Aster MIMS Hospital, Calicut, Kerala. Purposive sampling technique was used to select the sample. This was a descriptive study of 65 parents of children aged between 5-10 years visiting Aster MIMS hospital, Calicut. A pre-informed well written consent and ascent form was obtained from the sample.

Statistical Analysis

After obtaining these data, the results were transcribed into bar charts/ tabulations and statistical analysis was performed. Test of significance were used where-ever required appropriately.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section deals with analysis and interpretation of data collected to evaluate the parental attitude regarding junk food consumption among children visiting Aster MIMS Hospital, Calicut, Kerala. The analysis and interpretation of data of this study are based on data collected using the attitude rating scale.

	Extended Family	1	1.5
8	Standard of Education of Their Children		
	Lower Primary	27	41.54
	Primary	29	44.61
	Upper Primary	8	12.31
9	Type of school		
	Government	29	44.6
	Private	31	47.7
	Others	5	7.7
10	Type of transportation		
	Private vehicle	30	46.2
	School vehicle	21	32.3
	Public vehicle	8	12.3
	other	6	9.2

Section B: Analysis of parental attitude regarding junk food consumption among children

Section C: Analysis of association between parental attitude regarding junk food consumption with selected socio-demographic variables.

Study results shows, there is no association between parental attitude regarding junk food consumption with selected socio-demographic variables.

Rakshit Lakra and Dr. Priyanka Singh were conducted a study on family decision making on parental influence on children’s fast-food choice. studies show that, parents influence children’s eating patterns, especially fast-food selections. This study explores family decision-making processes to determine parental influence on children’s fast food habits. This was conducted among 5-15 years old families to determine how parental supervision, socioeconomic conditions and family dynamics after children’s diet. Parental influence is significant, children’s preference and external effects like peer pressure and marketing can influence fast food choices.

CONCLUSION

This study shows that parents having a satisfactory attitude towards junk food consumption among their children. Setting meal patterns, modelling good eating

and discussing nutrition with children substantially affect their diets and health. Children’s eating habits are influenced by advertisement, peer pressures, family atmosphere, parental attitude, school environment and so on. Education and availability of healthy foods can be help to reduce the use of junk food by children. Parents should act as a role model and should work for the policy changing in their life.

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